

Project Title: SpART: Spotlight on Artists in Recommenders Systems

Informed Consent Agreement

The purpose of this project is to understand how the current systems used to recommend music affect artists and how these systems could be used to increase the positive effect for the artists.

We will perform an interview with a small number of music artists to understand their perspective regarding music recommender systems.

Benefits: The main goal of this study is to identify potential problems in current music recommender systems that affect artists. Therefore, the benefits of the study include raising concerns in the community (including academic and industry) about these systems and propose alternative solutions that could benefit the artists.

Time required: The interview will take approximately 45 minutes, including max. 10 minutes for an introduction and ~35 minutes of questions.

Voluntary participation: Your participation in the study is completely voluntary. You have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality: All information is strictly confidential. With your consent, we will record the interview. Recordings will only be accessible by the research team. Only anonymized data will be reported in possible scientific publications and only short fragments of the interviews may be reported in a strictly anonymized way; this means that your identity as a participant will remain confidential at all times.

We do not share information with any third party. All the documents and recordings will be stored in secured resources at our universities. We minimize the risks of this study by anonymizing all the information that could possibly identify the participants. In case that this interview is carried out online (e.g., using a third party communication tool such as Skype), the research team does not have any responsibility for the third parties that are used for the communication.

For further information about this study contact:

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Agreement:

I have read the above information and understand the nature and purpose of this research. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw at any time. I understand that the results of this study will be treated confidentially. The results will be reported only in summary form and I will not be identified individually.

I agree to participate in the research study described above.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Optional Information

The following information will be used in potential future scientific publications referencing your music career without explicit identification. You can choose to leave any of these questions without an answer.

What is your age range?

18-25 26-35 36-45 46-55 56-65 66-75 76-85

What is your gender?

Female Male Other: _____

Where were you born? (city, country)

In which city do you live currently?

In which city have you started your music career?

If any, which are the music genres that you feel most associated with?

For how many years have you been active in the music industry?

How many albums/singles have you released to the current date?

If you have to put yourself under one of the following categories, which do you feel more identified with?

Newcomer Known in one country Globally known Other: _____

Are you signed by a major label (Sony, Universal or Warner) or by an indie label?
